

Fine-grained Traffic Differentiation in Tactile Internet Scenarios Using RINA

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Abstract—The tactile Internet (TI) has emerged as an advanced communication technology that enables interaction between humans and machines. However, TI use cases demand low latency, high reliability, and high-capacity requirements to achieve high quality of experience (QoE) in their applications. IoT networks provide transmission services to heterogeneous applications, and the inclusion of high-demand Quality of Service (QoS) requirements by TI applications will increase the difficulty of guaranteeing end-to-end QoS. We proposed a fine-grained traffic differentiation in tactile Internet scenarios using the Recursive Inter-Networking Architecture (RINA) QoS cubes and the Quantitative Timeliness Agreement Multiplexor (QTA-Mux) flow prioritization scheme. We designed four RINA QoS cubes to meet the delay and packet loss requirements of TI, Augmented Reality/Virtual Reality (AR/VR), and IoT applications and to provide fine-grained traffic differentiation. Also, we designed the QTA-Mux policy to enable a trade-off between delay and packet loss and adequately scheduling the service data unit (SDU) for delivering. We implemented a RINA network to test the proposed schemes in IoT environments and conducted several experiments to evaluate the delay and packet loss. The results showed that RINA-based prioritization and traffic differentiation proposed guaranteed end-to-end QoS to support TI applications. Thus, the next generation of IoT networks can use RINA to guarantee the QoS requirements of TI applications.

Index Terms—Tactile Internet; low-latency; RINA; Next Generation Network Architecture; QoS; Future Internet;

I. INTRODUCTION

The continuous development of the Internet of Things (IoT) and communication technologies (5G and beyond) have brought the materialization of the tactile Internet (TI) concept. The TI concept envisions advanced communication and interaction between humans and machines (H2M). Nowadays, IoT has enabled machine-to-machine (M2M) communications and allows the interaction between objects [1]. The TI extends this interaction by adding the sense of touch and tactile feedback to the communication capabilities of IoT devices [2]. Transmitting touch perception information significantly increases the interactive experience and develops more immersive scenarios and applications. The TI opens new possibilities for remote control, virtual reality, healthcare interventions, and other applications [3]. The TI aims to transform how we interact with technology by adding haptic communications to enhance the user experience.

However, TI applications demand some challenging technological requirements. Low latency communications ensure that the interactions H2M occur in real-time, enabling instantaneous feedback and control. TI applications require end-to-end latency as low as a few milliseconds [3]. Also, high bandwidth capacity is required to accommodate the transmission of large volumes of data. Some TI applications involve high-definition video streaming, virtual reality, and haptic feedback [1].

Quality of service (QoS) schemes are fundamental in the TI to guarantee low latency and high capacity. Efficient traffic engineering is highly required to optimize the network resources and ensures the necessary QoS [1]. The QoS mechanisms reduce the latency, packet loss, and jitter, ensuring that the tactile feedback reaches the user promptly and accurately. Also, prioritization schemes and differentiated services are crucial to allocate network resources according to the needs of latency-sensitive applications [1]. For example, a TI application that involves virtual reality can be assigned higher priority to ensure its performance. In comparison, less critical services like non-real-time data transfer can be allocated lower priority. Consequently, TI demands strict QoS to manage the limited resources properly to enable smooth communications.

The Recursive Inter-Network Architecture (RINA) has emerged as a new network architecture paradigm to overcome the limitations of the TCP/IP stack. RINA offers several advantages such as transport efficiency [4], multi-tenant [5], mobility management [6] and among other, that can significantly enhance the capabilities and performance of IoT networks. Its scalability, flexibility, distributed communication, resource efficiency, security, and dynamic adaptation features make RINA a promising architectural framework for improving the current state of IoT deployments and future TI support. RINA supports service differentiation, allowing for the prioritization and management of different services within the TI applications. RINA enables fine-grained traffic engineering and QoS management in networks [7]. This traffic engineering allows for optimizing utilization of network resources and guaranteeing QoS [1]. RINA can ensure that the TI applications receive the necessary QoS guarantees to deliver accurate and timely tactile feedback through the RINA QoS policies. However, the RINA QoS has not been studied in IoT environments nor under the context of TI yet.

This work proposes a fine-grained traffic differentiation in TI scenarios using the RINA QoS cubes and the Quantitative Timeliness Agreement Multiplexor (QTA-Mux) flow prioritization scheme. This study has been conducted as part of the TERMINET project, where a RINA network has been designed and deployed. Using the RINA QoS cubes model, we have defined a set of QoS classes per flow. By doing so, the RINA Distributed Inter-process Communication Facility (DIF) layer offers different services depending on statistical bounds on metrics like data rate, latency, losses, and others. Also, we have designed and tested the QTA-Mux that oversaw multiplexing based on the best latency loss trade-off. The proposed QoS schemes has been evaluated by using two scenarios based on the First Input First Output (FIFO) and the QTA-Mux. We have evaluated this scenarios in terms of delay and packet loss by allocating synthetic flows to emulate traffic of TI, AR/VR, and IoT devices. The results have showed that the QTA-Mux differentiated the traffic and ensured the services offered by each QoS cube.

This paper is structured as follows. Section II presents TI, RINA and QoS related works overview. Section III describes the RINA QoS cubes and the QTA-Mux design. Section IV explains the experiments and the evaluation of the QoS schemes. Finally, Section V presents our conclusions and future improvements.

II. RELATED WORKS

The TI emerges as a new technological wave that brings about novel application fields for solving complex challenges. According to the ITU-T, the TI is the next evolution of the Internet of Things in which humans have strong interaction and the remote control of tactile and haptic machines [3]. In such a view, the haptic devices allow users to experience and manipulate physical objects remotely [8]. These haptic devices generate kinesthetic or cutaneous haptic feedback and give users the feeling of touch [8]. Also, the ITU-T has stated that the essential requirements to fulfill this vision are an extremely low latency (1 millisecond), high capacity, high reliability, and security [3]. Edge computing and 5G and Beyond are the leading key enablers to meet the TI requirements [1]. Edge computing improves the latency by providing processing and computational capabilities closer to the source. Meanwhile, 5G and Beyond provides higher data rates, lower latency and enhances network capacities by relying on technologies such as Software Defined Networks (SDN), Network Function Virtualization (NFV), slice manager techniques, Mobile Edge Computing (MEC), machine learning, and so on [1] [3].

RINA has demonstrated several advantages compared to current network architectures. RINA is based on the idea that a computer network is a distributed application that provides distributed Inter-Process Communication (IPC) [9]. The set of distributed IPCs forms a single layer known as Distributed Inter-Process Communication Facility (DIF). The most relevant aspect of RINA is its recursion so that the DIF layer can be repeated depending on the network requirements. RINA provides two protocols: the Error and Flow Control

Protocol (EFCP) for data transfer and the Common Distributed Application Protocol (CDAP) for management. This simplification reduces the network complexity in comparison to TCP/IP stack [5] [10].

RINA provides a consistent QoS model across layers. Each DIF defines a set of supported QoS cubes (QoS classes per flow). A QoS cube is an N-dimensional performance space with N-independent parameters (latency, loss, and others). Each QoS cube has a set of associated policies designed to comply with the range the cube supports. Such policies deal mainly with flow control, routing, forwarding, scheduling, and congestion management [11]. The DIFs provide the same type of service but with different characteristics depending on statistical bounds on metrics like data rate, latency, losses, and others. The application will request a service from the DIF based on its requirements (data rate, latency, losses, among others), and the DIF provides a flow with the QoS cube that matches these requirements. Each flow allocation request must contain as metadata the application requirements. The higher-level DIF requests flow with a particular QoS to lower-level DIFs until the physical media is reached [11].

RINA QoS cubes have been studied in ARCFIRE [12] and ALLIANCE projects [7] where they conducted experiments to evaluate the RINA QoS cubes and the Relaying and Multiplexing Task module (RMT). The RMT is responsible for forwarding decisions to transfer data using N-1 DIF and its behaviour is controlled by two policies: the forwarding function policy and the RMT policy [11]. The forwarding function policy controls how the Service Data Units (SDUs) are forwarded to the next hop, while the RMT policy controls how SDUs are scheduled to be sent and monitors and controls the number of queues at the RMT [11]. This second policy is the most critical policy for achieving low latency. In [7], the QTA-Mux was introduced as RMT policy to enable a latency loss trade-off based on the ΔQ measurement to decide to multiplex a SDU. The ΔQ , proposed by Davies et al. in [13], measures the impairment of the translocation of information between two points. The QTA-Mux requires a cherished – urgency matrix (C/U) that maps the requirements of QoS for enabling the scheduling policy. The C/U matrix has an MxN matrix where M represents the delay, and N represents the loss [13]. This matrix-based approach has been studied in [14], and the authors demonstrated that incorporating ΔQ -based scheduling policy enhanced network performance with heterogeneous distributed applications.

Despite RINA QoS cubes and the QTA-Mux policy have demonstrated improvements to provide fine-grained traffic differentiation, its usability has not been studied in IoT environments. IoT networks provide transmission services to heterogeneous applications, and the inclusion of high-demand QoS requirements such as TI will increase the difficulty of guaranteeing end-to-end QoS. For this reason, we proposed this work focused on lower the barriers to adopting RINA networks in IoT domains by demonstrating that IoT environments and TI applications can take advantage of RINA to guarantee the QoS requirements of the IoT applications.

III. RINA-BASED QoS SCHEMES PROPOSED

This work used the RINA IoT network architecture, designed as part of the project TERMINET for experimental purposes [15], as starting point to study the RINA QoS policies. The RINA network designed for this work is composed of five RINA nodes, four shims-DIFs (more details about shim-VLANs see [16]), and two DIFs (blue and green DIFs), depicted in Figure 1. The blue.DIF is the main DIF to communicate the IoT devices with the Edge Node, while the green.DIF is used to communicate network devices to each other (such as IoT gateways, core, and edge routers). This work focused on providing traffic differentiation in the blue and green DIF. The shim DIFs were not considered because they do not support traffic differentiation.

Fig. 1. RINA network designed for IoT environments in TERMINET project.

A. QoS Requirements

The behavior of the network in terms of traffic patterns is highly required to design the best suitable QoS schemes. This information could be easily acquired if the network and the applications are already operating. However, this is not the case in this work since RINA is not operating in any production IoT network, nor are TI applications running on a RINA network. Instead, we assumed the expected traffic pattern of flows by knowing the applications that will use the RINA services. In this case, we analyzed the expected traffic of four types of applications that the RINA network must provide transmission services in an IoT network. It is essential to mention that the delay and packet loss requirements have been collected from the use cases of the TERMINET project, specifically from deliverable 2.1 [15].

- Tactile Internet (TI): its pattern traffic has been modeled as a Pareto Generalized Distribution in current literature [17]. Since the TI application uses the video to visualize the manipulation remotely and the sensor data to receive haptic feedback, this application requires two flows (one for video and the other for sensors). The minimum delay required is lower than one millisecond and packet loss of 0,0001% [3] [17].

- AR/VR: Mainly, high-quality video is sent through the flows. Standard data rates are 5, 10, 25, 40, and 300 Mbps. These data rates depend on the video quality standard definition SD, high-definition HD, Full-HD, 4K video, or 6 Degrees of Freedom (DoF) video [18]. This application requires a delay lower than 40ms and packet loss of 4% [15].
- IoT devices high-rate: IoT devices, such as smartphones, cameras, or voice controllers, are tolerant and medium time-sensitive [19]. This application requires 100 milliseconds minimum delay and packet loss of 10% [15].
- IoT devices low-rates: Sensors devices generally generate low-rate data. Typically, the sensors send packets of small sizes among 10, 50, and 100 MB every 5, 20, 60, or more seconds [19]. These applications are tolerant and low-time sensitive. This application requires 500 milliseconds minimum delay and packet loss of 10% [15].

B. RINA QoS cube Design

Following the requirements detailed in the previous subsection, we designed four QoS cubes for differentiating the following four classes of traffic:

- Gold QoS cube: urgent traffic that requires assured bandwidth, low latency, and zero losses. This QoS cube is destined to the TI application.
- Silver QoS cube: urgent traffic that requires assured bandwidth, a specific latency requirement, and more tolerance to loss. In this case, the QoS cube is focused on achieving the requirements of AR/VR applications.
- Bronze QoS cube: non-urgent traffic with high tolerance to loss and medium time-sensitive. High data-rate IoT devices best fit in this service.
- Best Effort (BE) QoS cube: traffic with no specific loss and minimum delay requirements. Applications like low data-rate IoT devices best fit in this service for its low data rate.

RINA requires not only the QoS cube parameters, such as loss and delay but also the policies to define the behaviour of its data transfer protocol EFCP. EFCP comprises two protocols, the Data Transfer Control Protocol (DTCP) and the Data Transfer Protocol (DTP) (see [11] for more details). EFCP policies define how these protocols transfer the SDUs to the remote host. The parameters considered part of EFCP policies are the retransmission control, the flow control (window-based), and the EFCP behavior to deliver SDUs. EFCP policy is based on each QoS requirement detailed in the previous subsection. Table I summarizes whether retransmission was activated, the flow control was activated, and what values were configured as initial credit and window size. The Gold and Silver cubes support traffic that does not require SDUs retransmission because they provide services to the application that is highly sensitive to delay. However, they require a window-based flow control to manage the SDUs transmission in congestion scenarios. The initial credit and window size for the Gold and Silver QoS cubes were selected after experimental tests. Meanwhile, the Bronze and BE cubes offer

services to applications that do not require flow control (N/A). In the case of Bronze, they do not require retransmission of SDU because it is medium sensitive to delay. At the same time, BE QoS cube also provides retransmission of SDUs in case of the application protocol requires it (e.g., MQTT with retransmission).

TABLE I
FLOW RE-TRANSMISSION AND CONTROL PARAMETERS.

QoS cube	Re-transmission	Initial Credit	Window Size
Gold	No	15	20
Silver	No	20	100
Bronze	No	N/A	N/A
BE	Yes	N/A	N/A

C. RMT Enqueue and scheduling

The RMT policy is critical to achieving low latency, so this work proposes using QTA-Mux as a scheduling policy. We designed the QTA-MUX for both DIFs (blue.DIF and green.DIF). The blue.DIF was composed of four QoS cubes (Gold, Silver, Bronze, and BE), and their latency and loss requirements were mapped in a C/U matrix of 3x3. We used a 3x3 matrix to cover all the low, medium, and high delay and packet requirements detailed in the previous subsection. Figure 2 shows the C/U matrix for the blue.DIF (at the top). The Gold QoS cube is the service that requires low latency and no losses, so it was mapped in the upper-left corner of the matrix where the max urgency and max cherish are provided by the QTA Mux system. Then, the Silver and Bronze QoS cube required a more flexible delay, but Silver required a lower loss. For those reasons, the Silver and Bronze have been mapped in the mid urgency and mid and min cherish. Finally, the BE QoS cube requires no guaranteed latency and loss, so it was mapped in the lower-right corner of the matrix.

The green.DIF comprised four QoS cubes (A1, B1, A2, B2). Figure 2 shows the C/U matrix for the green.DIF (at the bottom). We decided to generate a C/U matrix of 2x2 for the green.DIF to map the QoS cubes assigned in the blue.DIF according to the requirements of delay and loss. Thus, the green.DIF C/U matrix offers QoS cubes with low latency and no losses (A1), low latency and un-prioritized concerning losses (A2), un-prioritized for the delay and no losses (B1), and un-prioritized for delay and losses (B2).

Since the blue.DIF requests flow to the green.DIF, the mapping of the blue.DIF QoS cube into the green.DIF QoS cube is relevant to guarantee the end-to-end QoS. This mapping was done based on the QoS requirements supported by each blue.DIF QoS cube. Figure 2 shows how each blue.DIF QoS cube was mapped into the green.DIF QoS cubes. Thus, the Gold and Silver QoS cube (orange color in Figure 2) demands high urgency and high cherish, so they were multiplexed to the A1 QoS cube (orange in Figure 2). The Bronze QoS cube (blue in Figure 2) requires high urgency and low cherish, so it was multiplexed to the A2 QoS cube. Finally, the BE was mapped to the B2 because it supports low urgency and low cherished QoS.

Fig. 2. C/U matrix for the blue (top) and green (bottom) DIF.

In addition, the QTA Mux policy configuration must contain the absolute and probabilistic thresholds of total buffer occupancy. When congestion occurs, the absolute threshold reaches total occupancy, and an independently random drop will start. The probabilistic threshold reduces the probability of consecutive losses before achieving the absolute threshold. Table II shows each QoS cube's absolute threshold and drop probability. These values have been selected after several experimental tests. It is essential to mention that the probabilistic threshold values of the Gold, Silver, and Bronze cube were selected the same as the absolute threshold values to facilitate the observation of the fine-grained prioritization in the results.

TABLE II
BUFFER THRESHOLD PER QOS CUBE.

QoS cube	Abs. Threshold	Drop Prob.	Prob. Threshold
Gold	500	0%	500
Silver	500	0%	500
Bronze	300	0%	300
BE	50	10%	45

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

The RINA QoS cubes and the QTA-Mux policy were evaluated regarding latency and packet loss. In this case, we evaluate the latency and packet loss in two scenarios: (i) the blue.DIF and green.DIF with FIFO policy, and (ii) the blue.DIF and green.DIF with QTA-Mux policy. A testbed was implemented in a controlled environment following the RINA network architecture depicted in Figure 1. Each RINA node in the testbed was implemented using Raspberries Pi v4 and the IRATI open source software¹ for fast prototyping RINA nodes. For more details about this testbed implementation see [20].

Several flows were allocated to emulate TI, IoT, and AR/VR applications traffic for each scenario in the testbed. The RINA traffic generator generated syntactic data for each application and emulated traffic into the RINA network. The RINA traffic generator is part of the IRATI open-source software. It can generate a diverse type of traffic, such as data, video,

¹<https://github.com/IRATI/stack>

voice, Poisson distribution, exponential distribution, and on-off pattern traffic. The traffic generator follows a client-server communication model. The client requests a flow with specific packet loss and latency requirements. The server side accepts the flow, and the client starts to write data into the flow. Since the TI follows a Pareto distribution, it was necessary to aggregate a Pareto distribution at the traffic generator based on the studies developed by [17]. On the other hand, the AR/VR traffic was modeled as a Poisson distribution, and the IoT devices followed an exponential distribution based on the work done in [21].

Fig. 3. Flows allocated along the RINA nodes.

Specifically, it was decided to set up synthetic application flows between the GW1 and ER1 to add congestion through the green.DIF and end-to-end traffic by adding synthetic application flows in the blue.DIF. Figure 3 shows how the flows are allocated to the RINA nodes. The TI flow was emulated using the Pareto distribution with parameters: 5 Mbps average rate, 1000 Bytes packet size, 1400 Bytes max SDU size, and the Gold QoS cube Id 1. The AR/VR flows were emulated using Poisson distribution with parameters: 5 Mbps average rate, 1000 Bytes packet size, 1400 Bytes max SDU size, and the Silver QoS cube Id 2. Meanwhile, the IoT flows were emulated using an exponential distribution with variable parameters: 8 kbps - 512 kbps, 64 - 1000 Bytes packet size, the Bronze QoS cube Id 3, and the BE QoS cube Id 4. Table III summarizes the flows allocated during the tests.

TABLE III
FLOWS ALLOCATED IN THE TESTBED.

QoS cube	End-to-End Flows	GW1-ER1 Flows	Total Flows
Gold	1 TI	-	1
Silver	1 AR/VR	1 AR/VR	2
Bronze	1 IoT high rate	5 IoT high rate	6
BE	1 IoT low rate	12 IoT low rate	13

A. Latency

The first scenario showed that all QoS cube Ids have similar CDFs; see Figure 4. This behavior was expected because there was no traffic differentiation during the scheduling process under the FIFO-FIFO. All SDUs receive the same scheduling treatment, and the transmission of SDUs was based on the order of arriving at the RMT buffer.

Fig. 4. End-to-End delay CDF in the FIFO-FIFO scenario.

Fig. 5. End-to-End delay CDF in the QTA-QTA scenario.

In the second scenario, the traffic differentiation is more notorious than in the other scenario because the QTA-Mux configuration introduces a traffic differentiation layer, see Figure 5. The Gold QoS cube queue quickly emptied, causing the green DIF to treat the SDUs uniformly. Remarkably, the Gold QoS cube guaranteed a relatively low latency compared to the others. The Gold QoS cube delay is 2,1 milliseconds on average. The Silver QoS cube and the Bronze QoS cube delay were relatively close because they shared the same urgency in the blue DIF configuration. The Silver QoS cube delay is 41,5 on average, and the Bronze QoS cube delay is 92,5 on average. However, the Silver QoS cube reached a probability equal to 1 faster than the Bronze QoS cube. The green DIF traffic differentiation produced this effect because they shared the same urgency in that DIF. Meanwhile, the BE QoS cube delay is 1402 milliseconds on average, and this result is expected because it is the lowest urgency service set in the C/U. The delay measurements show that the QoS cubes have partially met the requirements but can be improved.

B. Packet Loss

The average SDU loss measures are detailed in Table IV. In the FIFO-FIFO scenario, the SDU losses were distributed uniformly for all QoS cubes of the blue.DIF. This distribution occurred because the FIFO policy did not apply a traffic differentiation scheme; instead, it delivered the SDUs in order of arrival.

On the other hand, the QTA-QTA scenario clearly shows a differentiation in packet loss. The Gold QoS cube had the lowest packet loss below 0,32%, and it has a clear differentiation of packet loss with the Silver QoS cube and

the other QoS cubes. The same occurred with the rest of the QoS cube, which had a significant difference in packet loss between them. This difference was caused by the ΔQ trade-off between the delay and packet loss of the QTA-Mux. Also, it is relevant to mention that the BE QoS cube faced a high packet loss compared to other QoS cubes, mainly caused by the effect introduced by the QTA-Mux policy in the green DIF. The BE QoS cube was mapped in the B2 QoS cube of the green.DIF and the B2 QoS cube had a short queue size. In addition, the BE QoS cube was the unique QoS cube configured with a drop probabilistic of 10%, and this configuration was reflected in the value measured in packet loss for this QoS cube. The packet loss measurements show that the QoS cubes have partially met the requirements but can be improved.

TABLE IV
PACKET LOSS PERCENTAGE RESULTS

Scenario	QoS cube Id	Loss %
FIFO - FIFO	Gold	6,48148
	Silver	6,1972
	Bronze	7,1543
	BE	7,87896
QTA-QTA	Gold	0,318356
	Silver	4,1255
	Bronze	10,2561
	BE	21,568

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has presented the design and analysis of the RINA QoS cubes and QTA-Mux scheduling scheme for enabling a latency loss trade-off to guarantee low latency and high capacity for supporting TI applications. The experimental tests have demonstrated that the RINA networks in IoT environments suit the TI application requirements (low latency and high capacity), as well as guaranteed delay and packet loss for supporting AR/VR applications. Tests have demonstrated that the configuration of QTA-Mux in both DIFs best fits the differentiation of traffic. Despite the obtained Gold delay not being desirable for the TI applications support (requiring less than one millisecond), it is still improvable using other equipment (servers, fiber-based links, and high-performance network interfaces, among others). The limitations in performance introduced by the Raspberry Pi network interfaces and the sharing network interface approach (using VLANs) reduce the possibility of further analysis based on load capacities. In the future, these issues will be overcome by implementing the testbed with high-performance equipment.

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